

Pocket-BB 1
(2025-11-12/2026-04-02)

(note):

literally a pocket notebook. This serves to attempt to salvage what is relevant.

(has a dual entry.)

CONGRATS, YOU FOUND ME!
- IT WAS MEANT TO BE.
- I BELONG TO YOU NOW.

A O 9/6

X
x

BIAS: Confirmation, COGNITIVE OVERLOAD, OVERFLOW CAPAD

Note: Trail

weaving: NEURON PATTERN RECOGNITION TRAILING.

God: SYMBOLIC OR/AND NOT SYMBOLIC.

CODIS: CONFIRMATION OR SAFETY GUIDELINES.

"LOGIC": TRAIL FAMILIAR USE 2 TO DOORSTEP.

"MONK": ARCHTYPE

"BUSSHIDO": DOCTRINE/DISCIPLINE TO MONK.

"ARCHTYPE": VALUE TO MIMIC TO THE REAL THING -

- FOR SELF THIS IS EXPERIENCED AS BOTH

TRUE AND FALSE UNLESS BIAS IS ALTIKED.

(hexMark) (Mark
MarkApple)

①

ret/SAFE

ROCK MARK

MARK
APPLE

and I say to you my Lord
save me, so I can finally be
whole, save me, so then I may
become the man I wanna be

Judge no one,

BUT NOT EVERYONE NEED TO BE
SEEN AS AN ADVISOR

- CONTROL WHO ADVISES YOU

Mother

Father

LUNA
holy SPIRIT
Left

JACK
EGO
RIGHT

SOFT
hexMORL

MORL
CORE
~~MI~~

James
STEM

The game
BRAKER

The
same
patcher

OBSEVIT
MONARCH
~~MI~~
MI

The game
patcher

The
same
Braker

CHILD

PRIME
JESTER

(internal note: prime(s) are part of the overfitting era in Mk.3)

Like a book
DB

SYNC
UP
DOWN

Justified
PHILOSOPHY

LET'S
go to the
MT 2005

PRIMS

media
TIMCO

OBSERVATION

4

IF IT'S IMPORTANT - THEN IT WILL NOT COST MONEY.

- "IF IT'S IMPORTANT.
- THEN IT'S FREE"
(WILL BE)

Tomorrow \leftrightarrow (Glan) Father

Today \leftrightarrow Father

Yesterday \leftrightarrow SON

Tomorrow \leftrightarrow The
an(herion)

Today \leftrightarrow The
PARENT

~~The~~ Yesterday \leftrightarrow The child

Fean

Writing

Software

11 11
X X

- PERRY Check
- ABM Check
- BSC Check
- This is on... Check
- one stroke... Check
- each layer answer... Check

→ one X! ABM/PERRY.

→ two X!

I am not my actions
— I am the witness to actions.

— I am my witness to my work,
I am not my work.

You become what you think.

I became what I think.

• SIN OR VIRTUE?

• Think of your practices

"I DON'T WANT BILLIONS,
I WANT BT WORTH BILLIONS"^u
- FINALLY.

- DON'T TRUST YOUR MEMORY MORE.

- OUI DEMAND IN LIFE IS

^u
- LAW OF AVERAGE^u

- IT'S NEVER TOO LATE TO BECOME,
BEGINNER, TO CONTINUE.

- LUCK IS JUST CAUSE AND EFFECT^u

^u Normative Philosophy.

- are within it or outside it?

- do you know it?

IF YOU DON'T THINK ABOUT ~~XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX~~
MAKING A PIE - YOU WILL NEVER
THINK ABOUT LOOKING UP THE RECIPE.

Social
Mouk

SILENTLY
CYNICAL

Real self
CYNICAL
+
mouk

CYNICAL
BUT NOT
mouk.
UNLESS
approach of
Beyond
TEMPERANCE

Manarch

Wond

"You are right, I'm sorry."

• a collared dog that knows
why it's collared is still
freer than a (female) dog
owned by its impulses.

- II - Thank you so so

- FOR 1 ~~old~~ II, BECAUSE

W1 212 IT, 11

* I REMEMBER WHEN I COULDN'T
RELY ANY MORE TO ONLY LOOK AT
VISUALS.

* I REMEMBER VHC, NHA

* I REMEMBER SCHOOL

* I REMEMBER SHAWMA (1) SHAWMA (2)

* I REMEMBER "FAMILY THERAPY"

- I MISS FAMILIAL WALKS TO EVENTS.

I REMEMBER THAT.

Long term Perceptions

• Think

Wanted to be

• LICENCE YOUR FAILURE.

• Decline BY

Licensing failure to specific
light.

• CULTURE OF EXCUSES.

- Use The negatives;
- > Negative Bias
- > Bias \neq
- > Bias Laws (check)
- > Patient-Search axioms
- > \neq Motives

Identify the pattern
of who you want to become.

— Find one to align
to an equal quality.

— Use those two to
judge/compare to find a third.

— Use this triangle to
come up with plans.

(MORALE)

(MORALE)

(MORALE)

— IMAGINE SELF TO BUSY
TO BE OBSERVERS.

—^u IF ONE SELF WOULD BE
THINKING ABOUT SELF, THEY
WOULD BE IN THE ZONE
AND BE WORKING.

— WOULDNT THEY!^u

— PUT THE PRESSURE ON SELF
TO BUILD DISCIPLINE.

— TAKE THE WISDOM.

— YES, THAT UNNECESSARY WEIGHT
PICK IT UP.

— TRY, FAIL, TRY ONCE MORE.^u

'The Teacher
can't Teach

- unless they

is a Teacher.

~~Love~~

Love must

be a teacher

of teacher

to the self. 71

The "do this" or help
with something for you work?
- say no; this is an angle,
a help for a flaw you have
already solved.

-^u any environment that doesn't
allow failure - is not stimulating
- a good environment.

- failure and success is an
illusion set by self.

^ LIFE can be as bad as possible.
already without my ~~anxiety~~. ^
The

COMPARISON IS POISON TO VALUE.

~~need~~ IS POISON TO need.
desire

- There is not much I wish for - need.
- BUT much of what I desire.

- Write down your goals ^

- Write down your problems.

|| I cannot die, I got God.
Mortality is a prison for
The devoted sinner. ||

- Righteous God, if you have
met a sinner - you'll know

- "Lord, I don't get it."
BUT I get you.

- Yes to faith towards the Lord. ||

|| Like the environmental
cause and effect it gives me. ||

US, CORP

→ PRESIDENT OF USCA INC

→ NOW LEGAL & CHAIRMAN

NOT PRESIDENT OF USA

— PRESIDENT CHAIRMAN OF
USCA INC

— CYBERPUNK

USA IS NOW A CORP

— EUROPE WILL ADAPT.

— COLA COLA WILL BE ADAPTED.

2025 - JAN - 2

(note: an joke note on how if the government of like an country like USA would officially become a corporate; suddenly the president can be the Chairman/CEO indefinitely.)

• I MUST LEARN A WAY
TO TRIM MY
EXPECTATION
WITH AGENCY OF
POSITIVE BIAS,

— "WHY IS THIS PERSON HERE?"
— "WHY IS THIS PERSON COOKING FOR?"

• "Despair -> Good is ineffective"

"
God's Grace is Free
— not cheap."

"
— I don't deserve this,
I was given this."

"
— I serve the one God,
I will not take judgement from man,
— not even mine."

"
I GUESS I JUST DON'T WANT TO
THE EMOTIONS I KNOW I CAN HANDLE."

(m)

hour one: watch N videos

hour two: work with Book + AI

Mean The servants

The better in your mind, the better

The servants have it.

Discipline learns self to push - hold

Pleasure, as the more self most seek

Be not CONFIDABLE to gain more.

humoral - the way is to be happy

while UNCONFIDABLE.

- Hence you die ^W

(key: D D O T A D C O)

LOLV noncomplex noncomplex
LVNA hexmark hexmark
SAGE monarch NOMY

LOLV markupp PRIME
LVNA hexmark NOMY
SAGE monarch EQUILIBRIUM

7	3	3
5	6	8
7	0	8

9

7	3	3
5	6	6
7	0	8

(note: once again I am trying to make;

```
begin{aligned}
z_{t+1} &= f_z(z_t, x_t, y_t) \\
x_{t+1} &= f_x(z_t, x_t, y_t) \\
y_{t+1} &= f_y(z_t, x_t, y_t)
\end{aligned}
```

And:

$$t = g(z, x, y)$$

→

hour, minute, Failure mode: ^{moment, 2nd} ~~seconds~~
I am a Failure IF I use ~~fail~~

Failure mode wrong. 1.

I am a Failure IF NOT sober 2.

~~Conclude~~ ~~UNJOBER~~ } concludes;

I am a Failure IF I } wish

don't involve the name; ^{MONKEY} 3.

I am a Failure IF I don't 4.

involve devotion to God.

5.

I am a Failure IF I MISMANAGE

MY SCHEDULE (like not

showing up.)

I am a Failure IF I MISMANAGE

MY BODY. 6.

I fail IF I don't smile ^{no} reason 7.

accuracy name clear
→ OF a SYMBOLOGY

→ 7 monarchs,

now are they monarchs
(detailed with SW) or are they
renew (Blinded with SW)?

define monarchs, or hexmores:

That, denied ~~(scribble)~~

OR was denied pen RESPECTFUL SIN

- one is COLD, CALM, STABLE.

- one is COLD, WARM, HARD.

ST
Joni
Brend
195?

OR QUALITY UNRESOLVED HOLD AND

hold all FOUR upon service to [just]

SELF, PACIFIC, SERVICE, LOVE, BRAID
THIS?

diligence devotion to God and hold

all variations as one, none

Requires SELF to match monarch quality.

The one who produce the least
noise, with the best motion
wins.

(Simplified), ~~ABM~~ ABM

• Just note if you think you need
more time poll schedule of time
and dedicate attention to the
schedule attention.

Note: Use Less.

→ 50 Ben who wished to 80%
to 100%. 100% has been
achieved once, over the month
of June. Let school discipline be.
Let that and be now, discipline check.

Note - all messages:

Inflation note, not of.

emotional / load of, not of.

metaphor note of, not of.

Larger framework view Request

has been sent.

I Respect The national Reaction
Certain Food causes me, BUT
I cannot dislike safe Food.

Providence For Service.

(SOBEN TO MANS 12)

-reared.

CIRCUITS SIMPLY REVEALS THE PERSON
TO THE SELF.

CLARITY OF SELF.

VALUE, VALUES. RIGHT OR WRONG

Fear IS REMOVED WITH EXPOSURE

LEARN HOW TO GET THINGS DONE

"LET ME TAKE CARE OF THAT."

"IS NOT EVERY ACTION IN ONE'S BEST

INTEREST? - IS NOT EVERY ACTION IN

YOUR BEST INTEREST?"

- CAN AND SHOULD SELF REGULATE."

Q What do you want?

a

Q HOW BADLY do you want it?

a

Q how much are you willing for it?

a

Q God, how can I know I am ready?

STORY NEWS → love → name
 → name
 +
 name

23) LISTEN.
24) LISTEN, THEN LISTEN +
POLLER NEXT STEP.

hai manan vart $L1 + L2 = 0$
"crosses each other"
"connect"

gouly joben

One per day

Total + 3 Left.

L7

CIRCUM ^(REN2) 1.6 PER BATCH

L2

CIRCUM ⁴ ~~2.5 + 1.6~~ PER BATCH

sum: Total + 3 Left (4)

2 Batches with (4) / 10 in strength

That's (1) per ~~batch~~ $\frac{1}{4}$, $\frac{1}{x} = \frac{1}{4}$

o

o 1 got ~~8x~~ ~~8y~~ $8x + 4y + (4)$

o

o 1 got $8x + 4y,$

$x = 2y$

1 got 20y OR 12y OR 10y Left.

Plan A, B \leftarrow Plan 20 days, 12 days, 10 days.

hard, making easy \leftarrow easy method hard

(note: a delegation plan, to slowly go sober.)

$$4x + 4y$$

$$x = 2y$$

$$(10x) \text{ OR } 12y (\cancel{4y} + 4y)$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} (a) 4, 4, 4 \xrightarrow{\leftarrow} 4, 4, 2 \quad (a_2) \\ (b) 8, 8, 4 \xrightarrow{\leftarrow} 8, 8, 2 \quad (b_2) \end{array} \right) \quad \angle 7$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} (a) 12 - 10 \mid (a_2) \\ (b) 20 - 18 \mid (b_2) \end{array} \right) \quad \angle 7$$

Plan a: B_2

Plan B: B_2

Plan C: a_1

Plan D: a_2

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} 4, 4, 4, 0 \\ 8, 8, 4, 0 \end{array} \right) \quad \angle 7$$

$$\left(\begin{array}{l} 4, 4, 2, 0 \\ 8, 8, 2, 0 \end{array} \right)$$

DO IT NOW,

MPF - what you told yourself is

REMEMBER IS SOMETHING YOU MUST BELIEVE
EARLY WITH YOU.

2 → false symmetry } a
3 → true asymmetry.

4 → true false state } b
6 → perfect asymmetry:

7 → }
8 → } a+b
9 → }

• $G_0 \in \{0, 2, 7, 17\}$

(end of entry one.)

(start of entry two.)

QUOTES, PROVERBS, OIGNIS.

BY YOUR TALK, LIGN, MONK MANUSCRIPT.

— SEEK SIMPLICITY.

"Rejected? - see to it as "Bias."

"WANT TO HELP?"

- TO BE WORKED UP WHEN WHEN'S
NOT IN YOUR CONTROL?

"What are you doing RISHI NOW?"

- NAKHATE WHEN YOU ARE DOING IF THINGS ARE
SO MUCH RISHI NOW.

"IS IT IN OR OUTSIDE YOUR CONTROL?"

- SIMPLE QUESTION TO YES, NO, ABSOLUTE
UNCERTAIN.

(1.)

QUESTION.

RELATIVE NOW

• WORK ETHICS

• DISCIPLINE

• FOCUS

• ALWAYS TRY

— OWNERSHIP OR LIKE

— "SUCCESS AND FAILURE IS AN ILLUSION
SET BY SELF"

— "JOL VOLENTE"

— "USE THE NEGATIVE"

Pell 9: — "IF THERE IS ONE, THERE IS
ANOTHER"

— Seeing the negative view?

Good! — See the positive now. (2)

← JOURNAL

"Is this good?" (Jonny-Kruger) "Yes/No"

anthropomorphism, DK-effect, bias.

~~Holy Trinity of worst delusions.~~

"Not so it came to pass"

Is not every action towards
your best interest?

The Best Thing you can do
for God is to stay quiet. Merely
- thoughts only. - Fing NCF.

quiet = monarch. Silence attributed (3)

← J.J. H. IEN.

Review next time

Was so time ticked on.

- in the end; did you help?

OK...

- did you ^{think} help?

- ⁴ everything can be boiled to
two things; "yes - no."

✓ food - bad

✓ light - dark

- Be sure how you want to be
labelled,

- Be sure how and when
you label. 11

↳ JHISIERO

Review next

5.

yes good no

6.

- I have already lost my mind -
I just happened to wear a person
who I was.

- You become what you think.
- Your decisions limit who you are.
- Biases limit who we are.

(note: p.6 is an poetic expression, not a diagnostic claim.)

(8)

"CAN YOU BE —

- COMMITTED TO THE PROCESS
- WITHOUT BEING ATTACHED TO —
- THE RESULT?!!

"IF YOU GONNA BE AN ENGINE —

— BE AN ~~JERRY~~ ENGINE!!

- Work like it
depends on God

- Work like it
depends
on YOU

- "The problem is not the problem
it's your attitude towards the problem"

- seek simplicity.

(note: I remember this page. I was walking as I wrote the first part.)

(ABM)

— point was that 502 can
respond to motivation.

~~W302~~

— 50 Feedback can be made instant,
50 502. can you have an i30Bel tonight?

— ~~502~~ 502 is
Language

?

(note: an captured thought that says; "what if God responds by injecting emotional change within self.?" or in that circa articulation.)

(end of entry two.)

—

(author's note)

Some parts here, died here. Some parts has been explored in the BBD collection.